

THE DRUG DEVELOPMENT PROCESS AND THE PREGNANT WOMAN

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Abstract:

Introduction: The drug development process in the United States includes extensive pre-clinical testing and a series of clinical trials designed to explore the safety and efficacy of a new drug entity. As part of this process, animal studies are conducted to assess the effects of the new drug on the reproductive process.

Method: These studies called developmental and reproductive toxicology studies, form the basis for the information included in the current pregnancy subsection of the drug label. The new drug's effects on the human fetus are gathered through post-marketing studies, usually observational registries. There is usually no information regarding the dose appropriate for pregnancy.

Result: The usual adult dose is assumed to be appropriate. Proposed changes to the current pregnancy subsection would replace the categories with narrative text, allow more detailed clinical management advice, including inadvertent fetal exposure, and provide a summary of risks associated with the drug.

Discussion: The sections on fertility, pregnancy and lactation would be combined, since they are continuum. A provision is also being made to incorporate information from pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic studies relevant to pregnancy.

Keywords: drug development, pregnancy, pharmacodynamic studies.

Introduction:

Most health care professionals know that drugs in the United States have undergone an approval process by the federal drug administration (FDA) and are then "approved for a given indication". (1) However, few practitioners really understand much about drug development what the FDA approval process actually involves and what "approval" really means. For those of us who predominantly care for either pregnant or potentially pregnant women, how the FDA drug approval process applies to our clinical care of pregnant women is even less well understood. Since 1979, the FDA has required information on the safety of drugs during pregnancy in the product information. However, this information is largely based upon animal studies, the results of which may or may not be relevant to safety in humans. Information about the appropriate dosage and frequency of administration for the pregnant woman is not provided nor readily available. This article will give a brief sketch of the drug development process, the FDA drug approval process, and the efforts of the pregnancy labeling taskforce at the FDA to provide better information for clinicians carrying for pregnant women.

THE DRUG APPROVAL PROCESS:

When a new molecule is identified as a potential drug entity it must first undergo preclinical testing (2). This portion of drug development defines the pharmacologic action of the molecule, its mechanism of action, and its specific targets or receptors. Usually these first studies are conducted in in vitro systems using intact cell lines, genetically defined or altered cell lines, and cell-free systems. Animal studies are next used to study the metabolism, efficacy, toxicity, and dosage of the new drug. An analytical method that can measure the concentration of the drug in plasma or serum must also be developed. The measured concentration of drug in body tissues is used to explore the drug's pharmacokinetics, that is its absorption, distribution and elimination, and the drug's pharmacodynamics, or its pharmacologic actions. Preclinical toxicology studies are needed to determine a safe dose for testing in humans. The ability of the new drug to cause cancer, or its carcinogenicity, and its ability to cause cell mutations, or its mutagenicity must also be studied. Overall this pre-clinical process takes on the average 5 – 7 years.

Organizing the data and information from these pre-clinical studies, the new drug's sponsor presents the FDA with an investigational new drug application (IND). These applications include the molecular structure of the drug, its pharmacology, toxicology, and the plans for study in humans. These first in-human studies are called phase I studies and are designed to explore the pharmacokinetics, pharmacodynamics, and toxicology of the new drug in humans. For most drugs, phase I studies are done in normal healthy volunteers. However, drug for certain therapeutic areas, particularly cancer drugs, anti-HIV drugs, and neuropharmaceuticals, the Phase I studies are done in patients with those diseases. The goal of the Phase I clinical trial is to

assess the safety of the new drug and its ability to produce a therapeutic effect. For every ten new drug that are tested in Phase I

clinical trials, only one will progress into phase II clinical testing. Phase II clinical trials are conducted in patients for whom the drug is designed as a therapeutic agent. These studies are designed to show therapeutic efficacy and to determine the dosage regimen for the new drug.

Developmental and Reproductive Toxicology Studies:

If a new drug survives Phase I testing and enters Phase II testing, the drug sponsor, or manufacturer, must begin full developmental and reproductive toxicology studies, referred to as DART studies. These are animal studies, usually conducted in mice rats, and rabbit, examining the new drug's effect on all aspects of reproduction, including oogenesis, spermatogenesis, fertility, fecundity, litter size, spontaneous reabsorption, fetal malformation, fetal size, and newborn pup function. Studies are designed using dose escalation with death of the pregnant mother animal as the endpoint outcome measure. The information from these studies is included in the drug labeling information. These are extremely expensive studies to perform and are only completed for drugs which show great promise during Phase II clinical testing.

Phase III clinical trials are conducted in larger populations of patients for whom the drug is intended to be used. Phase III trials define the clinical settings where the drug is effective or not effective because larger numbers of persons are exposed than in phase I or phase II studies, phase III trials uncover adverse drug reaction. These studies may be defined population, or they may be designed to explore pharmacoeconomic issues. Some studies may be mandated by FDA guidelines on drug development. Other clinical trials may arise from conferences held between the manufacturer and the FDA to discuss scientific and clinical issues that arise during pre-clinical and clinical studies. Usually 250 – 1000 patients will be studied in phase III trials. At times 5000 – 9000 patients are needed to provide enough data for extrapolation to the general population.

These combined phases I, II, and III trials take on the average of 6 – 7 years to complete. If a new drug successful and promising the drug's sponsor files a new drug applications (NDA) with the FDA. This application includes data from all the pre-clinical work, the DART studies, and clinical trials. Regulatory review takes at least 12 months to complete. The expenses incurred for the development of new drug vary from \$125 - \$250 million. Examining the whole drug development process, including drug discovery and development costs, the costs are clinical trials, and the cost of unsuccessful drug and studies, the cost of bringing a new drug to market to estimate at \$ 500 million.

Federal Drug Agency Review of New Drug Applications:

The regulatory review process at the FDA determines the adequacy of the information presented by the sponsor, the benefit-to-risk ratio of the new drug, and whether the new drug should be approved for use in patients in this country. If a drug is approved for a given indication a product label will be developed as a joint effort between the FDA and the sponsor. The product label will include a description of the drug, its mechanism of action, its pharmacokinetics, the indication for use of the drug, dosage guidelines, adverse reactions, and caution to consider in using the drug. On the basis of the product labeling the manufacturer can then market and advertise the product for the specific indication for which it is approved. Currently this includes drug representatives of the manufacturer detailing physician and other health care providers, advertisements directed at practitioners, and direct to consumer advertising.

OFF-LABEL USES OF DRUGS:

Once a drug is marketed, although the FDA regulates the manufacturer's promotion of its product, the clinician's use of that product is not regulated. Under FDA regulations the clinician can use that drug in patients, for purpose other than for what the product is indicated in the product label. These are so-called off-label uses. Some off-label uses are extremely well researched with an extensive published literature regarding the off-label use. Other uses are based upon anecdotal information or information gleaned from clinical experience. Generally accepted off-label uses are based upon clinical trials published in the medical literature or are based upon a body of expert opinion and are included in drug information sources such as United States Pharma Code Drug Information or American Hospital Pharmacists Drug Information monographs.

USE OF DRUG IN PREGNANCY:

For the vast majority of drugs, no clinical trials are conducted in pregnant women. Therefore, for drug with potential use by women in the reproductive age range, the FDA requires surveillance by the drug company for information regarding the drug's effects in human beings during pregnancy. These efforts are usually organized into registries of observational data reported to the company and gathered after marketing, referred to as phase IV studies.

Table 1. Federal drug administration pregnancy risk categories

Category	Description	Examples
A.	Clinical trials in pregnant women have shown no fetal risk of abnormalities.	Potassium chloride, thyroxine, vitamins in recommended daily doses.
B.	Animal studies have shown no risk, but there are no human studies. or Animal studies have shown adverse effects, but adequate and well-controlled studies in humans have failed to show a fetal risk. Animal studies have shown adverse fetal effects.	Prednisone, chlorampeniramine, cefoxitin
C.	There are no adequate and well-controlled studies in humans; therefore, the drug should be used only if the benefits outweighs the risk.	Acyclovir, methyldopa, theophylline, simethicone, carbamazepine, cocaine, betamethasone.
D.	Demonstrated human fetal risk, but use may be acceptable despite the risk.	Tetracycline, tobramycin, phenytoine, valproic acid, warfarin, cortisone.
X.	Demonstrated human fetal risk, risk outweighs any possible benefit	Estrogens, oral contraceptives, misoprostol, aminopetrin, iodides

Product Labels Regarding Use in Pregnancy:

Within the product table, however, information about the drug’s effects on reproduction, pregnancy, and teratogenic effects gathered from the DART studies is included. A drug is classified into one of five letter categories (A, B, C, D, or X) on the basis of risk of adverse effects on reproduction and fetal development, or on the basis of risk weighed against potential benefits (table 1). In the pregnancy subsection of the product information label, the majority of drugs marketed in the United States carry the statement that:

“There are, however, no adequate and well-controlled studies in pregnant women. Because animal reproductive studies are not always predictive of human response, this drug should be used during pregnancy only if clearly needed.”

The emphasis in the pregnancy subsection of the product information label is on drug safety: does this drug cause fetal anomalies? The assessment of risk and therapeutic benefit is left to the individual practitioner. The risk most commonly considered is the risk of fetal teratogenesis, irrespective of the gestational age of the fetus when therapy is needed. The effect of untreated maternal disease on either pregnancy outcome or the developing fetus is rarely assessed. No information regarding dose adjustment or frequency of administration during pregnancy is included in the labeling because the sponsor has done no clinical trials in pregnancy. The usual adult dosage is assumed to be effective during pregnancy.

Clinical trials studying therapeutic drugs during pregnancy are necessary because more women are delaying childbirth thereby increasing the chances that they will have an underlying medical problem which requires drug therapy during pregnancy, and because the profound physiologic changes that occur during pregnancy can affect drug pharmacodynamics, pharmacokinetics and efficacy. Known changes in maternal physiology during pregnancy which have been shown to affect drug distribution and elimination (pharmacokinetics) include: expansion of plasma volume, hypoalbuminemia, increase in glomerular filtration, and changes in hepatic drug metabolizing enzymes. A full discussion of maternal physiology changes affecting drug therapy can be found in recent article by Frederiksen and a chapter by Stika and Frederiksen.

The published clinical trials on pregnancy are usually small studies conducted by independent investigators. Recently, the Maternal Fetal Medicine Network, multi centered units funded by the National Institute of Child Health and Human Development (NICHD) for larger studies, has undertaken drug trials for common diseases occurring in pregnancy. But there is no mechanism established to incorporate information from any published to incorporate information from any published sources into product labeling or any compendium of evidence-based therapies during pregnancy.

THE FDA PREGNANCY RISK CATEGORIES:

Concerns about the usefulness of current pregnancy product labeling have been raised by clinicians who care for pregnant women and women of childbearing potential, by academic and speciality medical organizations, and by women health organizations. These concerns have centered around the FDA pregnancy risk categories for teratogenesis. The categories have given clinicians

the impression that the reproductive risk increases from category A to category X and that the reproductive risk within each category is similar. To illustrate that risk within each category is not similar, look at the category C examples in table 1. included here is the drug simethicon, which is not absorbed systematically and therefore not risk to the fetus, and the known teratogen, carbamazepine. To illustrate the risk does not increase from category A to category X, look at the category X drugs, which include all the oral contraceptives. The oral contraceptives are listed here not because they cause teratogenesis, because oral contraceptives are not thought to cause fetal anomalies, but because there is no indication for their use during pregnancy. Another example, are the many steroid preparations, some of which are category C, e.g., betamethasone, and some of which category D, e.g., cortisone. To address these concerns the FDA held a public hearing in September 2014 to obtain comments. Based upon these comments, five major recommendations for change in the pregnancy labeling were identified. These included: replacement of the categories with narrative text less subject to misinterpretation; provision of more detailed clinical management advice, including advice for inadvertent fetal exposure; a summary of risks associated with the product, including the setting where the toxicities occurred; a broader discussion of the data, both animal and human, upon which the risk evaluation has been made; and since reproduction is continuum combining the sections of fertility, pregnancy and lactation. In May 1999 the FDA issued a concept paper on pregnancy labeling proposing a new model for the pregnancy subsection of drug product labels. The proposal organizes information into three major subsections: a clinical management statement; a summary risk assessment, and a discussion of the data.

In addition to proposed changes in the pregnancy risk categories, the Pregnancy Labeling Taskforce at the FDA has been working also to improve the data obtained from registries maintained by the drug sponsors and to facilitate making that data accessible and included in labeling. S new regulation requires the sponsor to develop a pregnancy register and address the available data in labeling. Another initiative has been to include more pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic data from studies conducted in pregnancy in the product labeling. This involves a paradigm shift at the agency since the FDA's focus in pregnancy labeling has been on safety of the drug for the fetus. Inclusion of pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic data would address the needs of the pregnant women for therapy, which is both safe for the fetus and effective for the mother.

Lacking any guidelines for drug use in pregnancy, clinicians have sought the lowest dose of many therapeutic drugs during pregnancy, thinking that this would be less risky for the fetus. Less thought has been given as to whether the lowest dose was effective therapy for the mother and what effect adequate therapy had on pregnancy outcome. To explore these issues a joint NICHD-FDA workshop was held in September 2012, and a public FDA conference was held in December 2012. a mechanism to get existing clinical data into labeling and a guidance document for industry addressing pregnancy studies has yet to be developed.

CONCLUSION:

Although at this time, the needs of clinicians regarding use of drugs in pregnancy are unmet, there are initiatives underway at the FDA to address those needs. The issues being dealt with are extremely complex and require input from many different disciplines. The goal to provide clinicians with more useful information in the pregnancy subsection of drug labeling will shortly be met.

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